

INTERACTION OF ARABIC ACID WITH ACIDS AND NEUTRAL SALTS

By S. N. MUKHERJEE AND A. C. BHOWMIK

Interaction of arabic acid with hydrochloric acid and neutral salts like NaCl and BaCl₂ has been studied. The results suggest the occurrence of exchange between the double layer round the micellar anions and those in the intermicellar liquid.

In a previous communication results of studies on the interaction of arabic acid with bases having cations of different valencies, both by potentiometric and conductometric methods have been reported (Mukherjee and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1949, **26**, 277). The potentiometric titration curves have been observed to present the characteristics of a strong monobasic acid, while the conductometric ones show two inflexions: one corresponding to the neutralisation of the free acidity and the other to the total acidity with each of the bases studied. The total acidity was not constant but varied with the nature of the bases used for interaction in the order: Ca(OH)₂ > Ba(OH)₂ > KOH > NaOH. Results of conductometric and potentiometric methods, as followed in this case, however, showed excellent agreement amongst themselves.

This variation of the total acidity might be the result of a base exchange process going on at the surface of the micellar anions (arabate ion) as suggested in the previous communication (*loc. cit.*). In the present investigation an attempt has been made to throw more light on this aspect by studying the interaction of neutral salts with this acid in the expectation that, if there be any base exchange proceeding in this system, it will show the effect of the same with neutral salts also having cations of different valencies.

EXPERIMENTAL

The acid and the salts used in this connection were of Merck's guaranteed reagent quality and were dissolved in equilibrium water of specific conductance 1.2×10^{-6} mho at 35°. The arabic acid solution had a concentration of 4 g. per 100 c.c. of the solution and was prepared by electro dialysis (*cf.* Thomas and Murray, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, **32**, 676) of a specimen of gum arabic (B.D.H.) purified by the method of Bungenberg de Jong (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1938, **47**, 254). The solution so prepared corresponded with sol T mentioned in the previous communication (*loc. cit.*). Measurements were all carried out in a thermostat kept at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Interaction with Acids

The interaction of arabic acid with other acids was studied only in the case of HCl by noting the influence of this on the hydrogen-ion activity alone measured by the potentiometric method. A concentrated solution of HCl solution was added dropwise to the arabic acid solution and the p_H of the resulting mixture ascertained after each addition by the use of the hydrogen electrode. The maximum concentration of HCl did not exceed 0.24N in the

mixture. The arabic acid concentration in all measurements in this connection as well as for studying the interaction of neutral salts was 4 g. of the acid per 100 c.c. of the solution. A blank or control experiment was done by noting the changes in p_H when corresponding amounts of the same HCl solution were added to a volume of water equal to that of arabic acid solution used. The ultrafiltrate derived from the same arabic acid solution by passing it through a cello membrane (No. 600) was also tested in the same way with HCl solution. Results have been graphically presented in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

Of the three systems presented herein the arabic acid solution shows the least change in p_H . This therefore appears to possess some buffer mechanism within it, which works even with the addition of considerable amounts of hydrochloric acid.

The ultrafiltrate, on the other hand, shows a marked diminution of p_H when the amount of HCl added is small. At higher concentrations of HCl the p_H shows a slight but a well marked tendency to rise indicating a decrease in H-ion activity. The general picture of the change in p_H in the case of the ultrafiltrate resembles more closely the case of water than that of the arabic acid when small amounts of HCl were added.

The buffering mechanism of the arabic acid is not quite clear but it is possible to explain this if we assume that, in the arabic acid solution, the "arabate" ions remain as colloidal micelles round which there remains a layer of oppositely charged hydrogen ions bound, in consequence of which the H-ions in the former cannot register their activity by the potentiometric method. With increasing addition of HCl a considerable portions of the H-ions added become bound and only a part remains free to register their activity by slowly diminishing the p_H . In the ultrafiltrate the number of arabate ions is much fewer as shown by Mukherjee and Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 277). Hence with increasing addition of HCl the hydrogen ions are not retained bound to the same extent as in the parent solution. With increasing addition of HCl the anions aggregate probably due to the partial neutralisation of their electrical charge, which the adsorption of H-ions eventually brings about and the bigger micelles subsequently take up a larger number of H-ions, in consequence of which the p_H of the solution tends to show a slight increase, as in the latter part of the curve. This increase in size of the particles is warranted by the observation that at high acid concentrations both

the parent solution and its ultrafiltrate develop turbidity and the former tends to coagulate at very high acid concentrations.

FIG. 1A

The buffer capacity curves for both the parent solution and the ultrafiltrate have been worked out by potentiometric titration of these with NaOH by plotting db/dp_H against mean base in milliequivalents and presented in Fig. 1A. Both present but one inflexion in their titration curves as referred to in an earlier paper (vide Mukherjee and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*). These inflexions have been shown in the buffer capacity curves as well, but there appears to be one important point where the curves differ from each other. The curve for the parent solution shows a flat portion in the region of half neutralisation, whereas this part is not quite marked in the curve for the ultrafiltrate. The difference in the behaviour of these in their interaction with hydrochloric acid may be suitably linked with the difference in their buffer capacity curves for a probable explanation.

Interaction with Neutral Salts

Variations of hydrogen-ion activity, chlorine-ion activity and specific conductance have been studied with increasing addition of NaCl and BaCl₂ solutions to a 4% arabic acid solution both by potentiometric and conductometric methods. In each case a control experiment was carried out by the addition of corresponding amounts of the salts to water.

Hydrogen-ion Activity.—Fig. 2 shows that neutral salts do bring about changes in the hydrogen-ion activity of the arabic acid solution. BaCl₂ shows a greater depression of p_H than NaCl at corresponding concentrations. No blank experiment with water or HCl was done in this case because it is well known that neutral salts like NaCl or BaCl₂ cause little change in hydrogen-ion activity and the behaviour is quite different in nature from that

observed in the present case.* Increase in hydrogen-ion activity with addition of these neutral salts must therefore be the consequence of base exchange brought about by the cations, Ba being more effective than Na. The greater total acidity observed with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ in potentiometric and conductometric titrations of the arabic acid solutions as reported in an earlier

FIG. 2.

communication (*loc. cit.*) may thus be an outcome of greater efficiency of Ba ions to increase H-ion activity of the solution by replacement from the double layer surrounding the micellar anions.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

* For effect of neutral salts on the hydrogen-ion activity of water and HCl vide Harned "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solution," Reinhold Publishing Corpn. 1943, p. 487 and pp. 450-60 respectively.

Chlorine-ion Activity.—Variations in the activity of the chlorine ions were also studied and graphically represented in Fig. 3; by plotting p_{Cl} ($-\log a_{Cl}$) against concentrations of the neutral salts added. Chlorine-ion activity was measured by silver-silver chloride electrode prepared by the method of Noyes and Ellis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 2532) and standardised against a standard NaCl solution (cf. Harned "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions," Reinhold Publishing Corp., 1943, p.557) of known chlorine-ion activity at 35°.

A blank experiment with water alone for purposes of comparison was performed with both the salts and the results shown in Fig. 4. The graphs for p_{Cl} against salt concentrations (NaCl and BaCl₂) are overlapping throughout the course studied which signifies that the chlorine-ion activities of NaCl and BaCl₂ solutions at corresponding concentrations of these salts, expressed in equivalents, are almost identical at least in dilute solutions.

But when these salts are added to the arabic acid solution, BaCl₂ shows a greater Cl-ion activity than NaCl at corresponding equivalent concentrations (vide Fig. 3).

Specific Conductance.—Blank experiments for BaCl₂ and NaCl added to water is graphically shown in Fig. 5. Both these salts at the same concentrations show difference in specific conductance naturally due to a difference in their ionic conductance, Ba-ion having a greater conductance ($L_{Ba} = 55$ mho at 18°) than Na-ion ($L_{Na} = 43.16$ at 18°). When, however, these salts are added to the 4% arabic acid solution, the difference in specific conductance disappears almost entirely and the plots for the sp. conductance for the two salts run nearly coincident as shown Fig. 6.

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

This observation is interesting and suggestive. If we assume that both Na and Ba ions, when added in small quantities to a fairly concentrated solution of arabic acid (4% in the present case), can replace H-ions bound in the double layer and these H-ions can register their conductance in place of the added Ba or Na ions whose influence, though not entirely obliterated, is but small, we can find an explanation to this peculiar observation noted above.

C O N C L U S I O N S

Thus it appears that there is in all probability some type of base exchange going on in this system and the Ba-ion is more effective than the monovalent Na-ion. In this respect the present observations tally with those made in other systems by different workers (Mukherjee, Mitra and Mukherjee, *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1937, 1, 227, *et seq.*) so far as base exchange is concerned, because divalent ions like Ba have been generally observed to show greater base exchange capacity than monovalent ions like Na.

In the light of these conclusions it is now easy to understand why $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ should register greater total acidity than NaOH as observed previously (Mukherjee and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*).

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PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY
JADAVPUR, CALCUTTA
AND
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

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